

POSSIBILITIES OF EDUCATION AND SOCIALIZATION FACTORS IN THE FORMATION OF PERSONAL SPIRITUAL CULTURE

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Abstract: *This article describes the role and importance of education in the formation and development of the culture of the spiritual worldview in the process of socialization of the individual. The author focuses on the issues of education and upbringing, the formation of scientific thinking and the development of the intellectual potential of the individual in solving the problems of the stages of socialization.*

Keywords: *Personality, socialization, personality formation, education, training, spirituality, spiritual culture*

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ФАКТОРОВ СОЦИАЛИЗАЦИИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ДУХОВНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ ЛИЧНОСТИ

Аннотация: *В данной статье развёрнута актуальность образовательно-воспитательного в развитии духовного просвещения и культуры процесса в социализации личности. Автор акцентирует внимание вопросам обучения и воспитания формирования научного мышления и развития интеллектуального потенциала личности в решении проблем этапов социализации.*

Ключевые слова: *Личность, социализация, формирование личности, воспитание, обучение, духовность, духовная культура*

INTRODUCTION

The spiritual culture of a person is the main concept of the processes of education and socialization, and in the center of education and socialization is the culture of a person, which reflects the culture of society at the individual level. The study of the problems of education and socialization has significantly changed views on the influence of education in the formation of the spiritual culture of a person. Because upbringing and socialization began to be considered not as separate social actions, but as a specific part of a set of social influences on the development of personality. Socialization leads to the achievement of —personal growth of the whole society using certain means and methods, and ultimately prepares the ground for the increase and further development of national cultures in these social spheres.

It is known that socialization is a set of all social processes that help to master (adapt) all forms and methods of social life and develop one's own values (self-awareness and self-expression). Socialization is the process of acquiring social experience and developing social relations, which is characterized by two stages - personality formation and development.

The main result of socialization of a person is the formation of characters determined by a certain position in society and required by society. In the process of socialization, the development of a person occurs as a result of the implementation of a number of tasks objectively facing him at each stage. At all stages of a person's formation, he solves vitally important, socially important, increasingly complex tasks - cognitive, moral, spiritual-educational, communicative, worldview formation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

When talking about the tasks to be solved by purposeful socialization, it is impossible not to touch on the concept of "education" that is part of the concept of "socialization". "The more perfect the education, the happier the people will be," say the sages. In order for education to be perfect, it is absolutely impossible to allow a gap to appear in this matter. Today, the world is becoming more and more fierce in competition, contradictions and conflicts. Threats such as religious extremism, terrorism, drug addiction, human trafficking, illegal migration, and "mass culture" are increasing and are undermining the beliefs and family values that have been practiced by mankind for centuries. That these and many other threats cause serious problems in human life is a fact and no one can deny it [1].

Education is one of the central concepts of pedagogy. "Education is aimed at shaping the image of a modern person by passing on positive qualities that ensure longevity to generations. It stabilizes the ability to think and think, to feel the sense of freedom and faith, to strive for justice and truth, to acquire worldly knowledge and to live according to these values in life" [2]. The role and importance of systematic and specific goal-oriented education in the formation of a person's spiritual culture is immeasurable. In this case, special attention is required to self-education, which is considered an important direction of individual approach to each person and development of moral culture.

Education is a unique mechanism for managing the process of socialization. In this approach, education has two main functions. The first is to simplify the entire spectrum of influences on the person (physical, social, psychological, etc.), and the second is to create conditions for accelerating the process of socialization in order to develop the person. In accordance with these functions, education requires scientific potential to overcome and mitigate the negative consequences of socialization, to give it a humanistic spirit, to predict and build pedagogical strategies and tactics. The main criteria of culture make it possible to distinguish the leading directions of education and socialization of a person. This is, first of all, the culture of the individual and society. The culture of self-management ensures the harmony of a person with himself, and it consists of components such as intellectual, emotional, physical, psychological, regulatory, creative and spiritual culture.

Socialization and education serve as subsystems of the integral process of personality formation. To confirm this fact, we can consider the subsystems of integrity - the characteristics that describe the unity, uniqueness and inconsistency of these processes. The unity of socialization and education means that these processes cannot exist separately from each other. The peculiarity of socialization and education is characterized by the fact that these processes are not absolute, but relative and can become one another under certain conditions. Education reflects the process of formation and development of individual characteristics and qualities, and "socialization" is a broader concept - the process of mastering the essence of the individual. Therefore, education is included in the process of socialization as one of the most important forms of relations between society and an individual.

The spiritual culture of a person determines the society's attitude to innovations, provides adaptation mechanisms, allows to adapt to the changing conditions of the material and spiritual life of a given society. In scientific literature, the concepts of culture and personality are considered as an inseparable unit. Personal culture is a set of characteristics (knowledge, qualities, habits, ways of achieving plans, values, creative achievements) that allow to live in harmony with the universal, national culture, to develop both society and individuality. Seeing that individual culture

is directly related to society culture, it should be noted that society culture cannot be reduced to the sum of individual cultures of members of this society, and individual culture is not a mechanical cut from society culture. At the same time, personal culture is not only a certain result of the influence of society's culture, but also a source of its development.

The concept of "Education" for grades 1-11 of general secondary educational institutions in our country will be discussed by the general public and introduced into the education system next year. This concept is being introduced in the general secondary education system in order to ensure the appropriate spiritual development of students and to form active citizenship competencies. The science of education studies the reality and phenomena that determine the development of the human personality in the course of the purposeful activity of the society. Culture in the science of education should be considered as the ability of an individual to master and use the achievements of society. We can say that culture is important in shaping a person as a person. In the process of socialization, a person becomes an individual, a member of society, an active person, that is, the knowledge, language, symbols, values, norms, and customs of his people, social group and the whole humanity develop.

The level of personal culture is determined by its socialization - acquaintance with cultural heritage, as well as the level of development of individual abilities.

However, the truth is that recently there have been many people who know all the changes in this life and can get out of any situation. But their cultural level is very low. It is the result of socialization divorced from real culture. It should be remembered that acquaintance with culture, education and socialization develops according to different laws.

RESULTS

Today, major crises are observed in almost all aspects of human life - economic, spiritual, political, ecological. According to the Russian philosopher L. I. Belyaev, we are living in a very complicated time in all respects. This is the period when it is necessary to change the paradigm of our thinking, to change the purpose of human vital activity in order to save life on this planet [3;26]. Complexity, especially the root causes and timing of crises, goes back to the time when man began to exploit nature. As we know from history, if we study the collapse of great empires, we can observe that its cause goes back to the spiritual crisis. In particular, this danger is the most characteristic aspect of modern humanity.

According to Abdurauf Fitrat, "The greatest of all the blessings that Allah has given is the mind, and this mind has made people noble and honorable among the creatures." The Almighty God has given us the mind to distinguish right from wrong, interest from harm, to choose what is right and useful, and to reject what is harmful and false. It should be known that the greatest blessing of God and the beginning of the happiness of the two worlds is the mind. When every person grows up, he has to enter the society and fight to ensure happiness. Only a person who embodies these three things can win in this arena. It consists of three things: wisdom, common sense and good morals. It is inevitable that a person who lacks one of these three things will be defeated in this struggle" [4].

DISCUSSION

From the above, we can understand that in the process of education and socialization, we should form the spiritual culture of a person in such a way that our children grow up to be people who do everything intelligently, and strive for spiritual, physical and mental maturity.

From a philosophical point of view, there is one main reason behind the spiritual crisis, spirituality based on the psychology of consumption, not creation, is a dry scientific thinking that does not take into account the standards of the heart, conscience, and morality, and is focused on profit. Therefore, it is necessary to bring scientific thinking to a harmonious level with rich, meaningful, deep and limitless figurative thinking. Achieving this result is not far from the possibility, but it is related to the assimilation of our national cultural values, rich history and spirituality, making additions to it suitable for the times and national interests. In short, today's times are changing rapidly. These are the ones who feel the changes the most. Let the things be in harmony with the requirements of their time. But at the same time, he should not forget his identity. Let the call of who we are and the descendants of great people always resonate in their hearts and encourage them to stay true to themselves.

CONCLUSIONS

As our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "What will we achieve this at the expense of?" Education, education and only education. But education is not only school education. Now we are all used to blaming the school. What about the neighborhood, the family, the wider community? "There is time left to understand the true meaning of the saying that a child has seven neighborhoods, both father and mother." The time has come to understand and live on this basis.

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